

Evolution of Ram Sharan Sharma as a Historical Materialist: The Little-Known First Chapter

Vishwa Mohan Jha

No scientist has always been right, and therefore, science does not defer to authority. What must remain sacrosanct, instead, is observed data, in so far as it is collected accurately, and the scientific methodology in all its rigour.¹ (*The Indian Express*, Editorial: 10).

Introduction

Ram Sharan Sharma enriched and popularised the idea of change in early Indian history, through his own example and influence. Our appreciations of his contributions have rightly focused on this feature of his voluminous scholarship ranging over more than six decades. Thus, his book *Light on Early Indian Society and Economy* (1966) was hailed as 'a dynamic view of early Indian society' by Romila Thapar, who noted how 'Sharma has attempted to locate reasonably well-defined changes during the period from 2600 B.C. to 1200 A.D.' – unlike 'most historians [who] have described the social structure of early India as *a fully evolved system from the very beginning* and which continued to exist in an unchanging manner throughout the period of early Indian history' (Thapar 1966: 74; emphasis added).

D.D. Kosambi, Sharma's illustrious predecessor, also identified a variety of changes through the entire course of Indian history (not just its early part), though of very different kinds and of much greater complexity. While there is much in Kosambi's writings that remains to be discovered, or has been identified with acceptable accuracy, it may be agreed that he opened up whole new vistas of change.

It is therefore something of an irony that historiographers should have failed to do the twin lodestars of early Indian history what they did so productively for Indian history. Instead, they have assumed – possibly unaware – that both were 'fully evolved from the very beginning'.

Just one illustration should suffice. In a survey of the historiography of women in early India in 1988, U. Chakravarti and K. Roy noted the exceptional significance of Sharma's 'recent contributions (1983)', referring to his essays on promiscuity, women and marriage in his book *Perspectives in Social and Economic History of Early India*, published in 1983. But it was not correct to refer to these as 'recent' – as 'a series of articles on social history in the 1980s' (Chakravarti 2006: xxix, n30) – for they had been there in the previous edition of the book, in the already mentioned Sharma (1966). This was noted by another scholar,

who reconfigured their historiographical significance, but again without success, and rather problematically:

As early as 1966, he [Sharma] included a study ... in his *Light* ... which reappears in his *Perspectives* ... as 'Co-References to Women and Sudra in Ancient Indian Literature'. ... It is important to bear in mind that it was long before feminism and gender history had become fashionable that Sharma had been concerned with these issues. What is significant here is that the questions which Sharma put to his textual sources were far ahead of his times. (Veluthat 2012: 133; also Shrimali 2011: 46).

Three remarks are in order here. First, it is significant for early Indian historiography and Sharma's intellectual formation that his interest in these issues goes back to neither 1983 nor 1966, but to early 1950s, the said article on women and *sūdras* having been published in 1950 in Hindi (Sharma 1950). Second, feminist history is not a matter of 'fashion': then as now, it is as *engagé* as nationalist or Marxist history. Third, in so doing Sharma was keeping step with – not moving ahead of – the revolutionary times.

There is an obvious disconnect between these essays and Sharma's other well-known works. It is thus only natural to believe (Chakravarti and Roy 1988) that he did not have a feminist perspective as such. In fact, placing these essays in their original context of the 1950s will show his perspective to have *then* been radically feminist – to the young Sharma, history was basically about the emergence and development of 'class-divided patriarchal society'. But this Marxian perspective on feminism did not derive directly from the Masters – although Sharma had started reading bits of Frederick Engels' *Origin of the Family, Private Property and the State* – but chiefly from the communist S.A. Dange's *India from Primitive Communism to Slavery*. Dange (1949: 77–79, Chapter IX) highlighted the 'slavery' of women as a major theme of ancient Indian history. Significantly, Sharma speaks in his 1950 article (and probably only here) of the 'slavery' of women in this sense: both women and *sūdras* figure so often together in early Indian literature because both had been condemned to 'आजीवन दासता' ('lifelong slavery') (Sharma 1950: 191).

It is a rare instance when an older view of Sharma has been treated as a recent one. It is generally the other way round, thanks to the assumption about his being 'fully evolved from the beginning', and is reinforced by the second assumption about what a Marxist historian must be like.² Sharma is believed to have *always* accorded, like any other orthodox Marxist, the greatest importance to technological and economic factors, e.g., the ground-breaking (literally too!) importance of iron technology; to have always been a crusader against communalist falsification of history; and so on. Sharma's own later reminiscences and self-observations have helped this impression not a little.

In fact, Sharma, whose fervent cry 'no production, no history' as the

General President of the Indian History Congress (IHC) at its Aligarh session was to elicit a characteristic response ('without culture, no production') from the fellow Marxist E.P. Thompson in its next session (Sharma 1975: 4; Thompson 1977: 264), came to write his first small piece on the history of production (Sharma 1957) well after the end of what I see as the first phase of his writing career. And till 1968 at least, R.C. Majumdar was to Sharma one 'sober' historian with no communal prejudices, as he was most certainly not to I. Habib in his frontal attack on both the Hindu and the Muslim 'communal schools' of history-writing – represented by Majumdar and K.M. Munshi, and by I.H. Qureshi respectively – at an IHC symposium on history and national integration (Habib 1961).

To be sure, Sharma was from the outset as free as anybody else of Islamophobia, and could in passing even be a tease – as when he combines the *Aryans* with the Muslims as the two most important groups of 'outsiders who came to [settle down in] India' (Sharma 1953: 191, emphasis added). However, regular attention to communal prejudices becomes a significant feature of his writings much later. They do not figure at all in his numerous historiographical discussions for a long, long time. When they begin to do, it is significant that he should date the beginning of 'the communal approach' to history writing only from 1980, and distinguish, rather untenably, the practitioners of the 'communal approach' from the 'Hindu nationalist/revivalist' sub-group within the broader category of 'nationalist' historians, so that the writings of Majumdar betray 'a ... [very strong] element of Hindu revivalism' rather than any 'communal approach' as such (Sharma 1991: xxiv; Sharma 2005: 9, 11–12).

The task as suggested by the paper's title is less easy than it might look at first glance. So the present attempt cannot be anything but preliminary and tentative in scope, limited by the references cited and so liable to be modified by what I have not been able to observe/consult.³ Further, we discuss only a small number of issues, chiefly those of method and largely confined to the formative first decade of his writing career up to, say, the late 1950s. In investigating the output of a lifetime of ceaselessly prolific career, shaping and being shaped by a plurality of contexts, it is likelier than not that I shall be making errors of both fact and judgement, of omission as well as commission. Hopefully, the readers will spot them sooner than me.

This first phase remains all but unrecognised in the numerous critical appreciations of the work of Sharma. When S. Jaiswal, the noted historian and probably his first PhD student, calls *Śūdras in Ancient India* 'his first major work' without so much as mentioning any of the previous 'minor' ones, and when B.P. Sahu, among the more dynamic of his last student-historians, dates them all 'from the later 1950s', they represent a near-consensus (Jaiswal 2014: 700; Sahu 2013: 116 (also pp. 114, 152, 239); Ali 2012: 8). As we set out to trace the becoming of Sharma's being, we need to move away from this consensus, and prejudge nothing.

Need and Nature of the Task at Hand

The Need

In assessing Sharma's influence on the practice of ancient Indian history, a comparison with Kosambi seems almost mandatory. Kosambi is generally regarded as the more influential of the two, including by Sharma himself (Sharma 1983a: 21-22 n9; see also Sharma 1989: 1).

However, it is perhaps truer to say that, on the whole, Kosambi has been more often simply celebrated (or dismissed) than studied and cited in earnest, especially till his birth centenary. That is to say, the citations of Kosambi are more often superficial or narrow than substantive; a point or two from his work (mostly one of his two books, *An Introduction to the Study of Indian History* and *Culture and Civilisation of Ancient India in Historical Outline*) is noted and then repeated *ad nauseam*, as if he had nothing else to say on the issues in question, be it the role of iron or feudalism. By all accounts, it was Sharma's versions of ancient Indian history that came to rule the roost from about mid-1960s, whereafter Kosambi began to be moved to the shadows after paying the initial homage. Whether it is the settlement of different parts of the country, importance of iron, meaning and implications of land-grant inscriptions, nature of the Mauryan state, or fortunes of trade and urbanism, it is Sharma's version that has been at the centre of discussions: often we seem unaware of Kosambi's take – his evidence, reasoning, and conclusions – on these and other matters, or assume he did not have any, or, worst of all, impute to him the ideas of Sharma. There have been all kinds of evaluation of the respective works of the two savants, as well as of the influence of Kosambi on Sharma. This we have surveyed in a separate larger study on Kosambi, not yet published.

Sharma's influence on the historical profession and its practitioners in India runs deeper than one may imagine. It appears to be incalculable indeed. We may begin with two examples – one of an arch-critic of Sharma (B.D. Chattopadhyaya), the other of an arch-follower (D.N. Jha). The critic has turned out to have been, quite unexpectedly, an arch-follower of Sharma at the early stage of his career, while the arch-follower is seen, as surprisingly, to have over-followed Sharma to an extent not realised

In 1975, Chattopadhyaya prepared (with the assistance of V.R. Mani) and submitted to the Indian Council of Historical Research a manuscript, comprising extracts from primary sources with prefatory notes of substantial merit. It was published in 2000 as *A Sourcebook of Indian Civilisation*, with the addition of a considerable Appendix by Ranabir Chakravarti – under the misleading first name of Niharranjan Ray, who was a mere General Editor of the three-volume project. In these prefatory notes, we see Chattopadhyaya subscribing *in toto* to Sharma's ideas on early medieval India. On economic trends during the Gupta period, he almost paraphrases Sharma: first, land grants to brāhmaṇas led not only to

agrarian expansion but 'new land relations' as they 'must have gradually imposed some measure of immobility and several feudal-type obligations on the cultivators, who also had to suffer an increasing burden of taxation'; and second, 'at least a partial decline of trade' attested by evidence both of coins and settlement archaeology (Chattopadhyaya 1975: 356–57, 364–65). For the post-Gupta period, citing the same passage from the law-books about 'the *svatva* of the King, the *svatva* of the landowner, the *svatva* of the tenant farmer, and even the *svatva* of the mortgagee in possession' as Sharma had done (on J.D.M. Derrett's authority) in his *Indian Feudalism*, Chattopadhyaya describes, in full agreement with Sharma's thesis, how 'the King himself was assuming a clearer right of ownership of land' and bestowing it upon the assignees that 'could result in the appropriation of former ownership rights' of peasants and 'could reduce the peasants to the position of serfs'. In fine, 'the proliferation of landed intermediaries all over the country ... left the cultivator with hardly any share of his produce' (ibid.: 443–44). For trade, it is the story of decline and revival, with no evidence for revival cited from before the eleventh century and with not a word from the rich empirical critiques of Sharma by Sircar (ibid.: 450–60). The headings under which sources are arranged include 'emergence of increasing number of intermediaries', 'duties of feudatory chiefs', 'feudal titles', 'feudatories offering tributes', and 'proliferation of castes' (ibid.: 444, 465, 471, 478).

No one has highlighted the importance of Sharma's works more than D.N. Jha did in the bibliographical essay of his work *Ancient India: An Introductory Outline* (1977). Jha set out to write an original work, but did not succeed entirely – on account of Sharma's influence on him, paradoxically. Over the decades, as Jha read the proofs and prepared the indices of Sharma's books, read and took notes from Sharma's works for teaching and research, and lent him an ear as a pupil and then as a colleague, he came to bear Sharma's imprint in ways he did not obviously see. In his *Ancient India*, Jha did not just paraphrase Sharma every now and then, but – unwittingly in all likelihood – practically repeated the same sentences.

For instance, Sharma wrote:

Desire is expressed for *prajā*, which might include both boys and girls. But really people were keen on having brave sons (*suvīrāḥ*) who might fight their wars. ... In some cases a woman could freely carry on love affairs. She could take part in sacrifices along with her husband, and some women are credited with the authorship of the Vedic mantras. Clearly in R̥gVedic times mother-right was not completely submerged by father-right. (Sharma 1968: 265).

Jha writes:

In the hymns desire is expressed for *prajā*, including both boys and girls. But the people seem to have been most keen on having brave sons (*suvīrāḥ*)

who might fight their wars. ... In some cases a woman could freely mix with young men and carry on love affairs. She could also take part in sacrifices with her husband. Some women were also said to have been authors of Rig-Vedic hymns. ... Clearly the mother-right was not completely submerged by the father-right in this period. (Jha 1977: 16)

To Sharma's admirers, it seemed difficult to imagine that he could make mistakes. Varāha-mihira is dated by all accounts to the sixth century AD (though he could have been born towards the close of the previous century), whether we go by the Śaka Year 427 (AD 505) – the reference point in his *Pañcha-siddāntikā* – or by the Śaka Year 509 (AD 587) of his death. But Sharma placed him, in speaking of his *Bṛihat-saṃhitā*, in the seventh century in one of his articles in 1971, reproduced in his *Perspectives* (Sharma 1983a: 95, 98). B.N.S. Yadava, however, refused to see any mistake here, and argued that Sharma must have had the following in mind:

Varāha-mihira is generally assigned to the last quarter of the fifth and the first half of the sixth century AD (Ajay Mitra Shastri, *India as Seen in the Bṛihat-saṃhitā of Varāha-mihira...* 1969, p. 16). However, there is definite evidence of some interpolation in *BS* [*Bṛihat-saṃhitā*], which is regarded as his last major work. It is probably in view of this that R. S. Sharma has assigned this work to the seventh century. (Yadava 1980: 285–86 n11)

However, Shastri in his review of the book pointed to the seventh-century ascription as an error, 'probably the printer's devil' (Shastri 1983: 234). Unfortunately for Yadava, Sharma came round to Shastri's view in his *Urban Decay* (1987) in regarding Varāha-mihira as 'an astrologer who lived in the last quarter of the fifth and the first half of the sixth century' (Sharma 1987: 109 and n8). In doing so, Sharma abandoned not only the seventh-century dating but also his still earlier adherence (in the *Śūdras*) to the standard bracketing of Varāha-mihira between AD 505 and AD 587 (Sharma 1958: 223 n7). In the next edition of *Perspectives*, the date of the *Bṛihat-saṃhitā* was quietly corrected (explicitly and by implication) to sixth century AD (Sharma 1995: 17, 135, 138).

The overpowering influence of Sharma is undoubtedly to be related to his formidable professional clout, particularly in the ascendant from sometime after 1965, till which time his influence was yet to overtake Kosambi's. Thus in the essay that Habib wrote on the social distribution of landed property, which was published in *Enquiry* in 1965, the pride of place is assigned to Kosambi throughout the citations and discussions; recognition is taken of the importance of the just published *Indian Feudalism*, but in general Sharma figures as at best a distant second, or else like any one of the many other authors consulted. Sharma's essay on the stages in ancient Indian economic history, which was being so widely celebrated then for its historiographical significance, bore so closely

on Habib's survey, and had been published in 1960 in the same journal *Enquiry*, is cited just once for its reference to the work of D.H. Gordon and without naming either the author or the title!

'Fossils', Not Contradictions

There is an additional reason why we must read Sharma's works in the order they appeared: to ensure fair hearing and preclude misplaced criticism. Attention to the time dimension helps to distinguish issues of evolution from matters of contradiction.

The distinction may be illustrated through a comparison of certain common matters in his two books – *Śūdras in Ancient India* and *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions of Ancient India*, published in 1958 and 1959 respectively. In the first book, Sharma dwelt on the wrong usage of the term 'serf' by Indologists, explaining it as a person attached to a piece of land, and criticised the frequent mistranslation of the śūdra as a 'serf'; nor could the śūdra be seen as a slave (Sharma 1958: 46–48; however, cf. 45–46).

In the same work, Sharma meticulously explained three other terms – *dāsa*, *karma-kara* and *bhṛitaka* (Prakrit *bhataka*) – as meaning respectively a slave, a hired labourer/worker, and a hired worker, though a broader category than *karma-kara* (Sharma 1958: 97–98) and also translated as a servant. Thus, we learn of 'slaves and labourers' in the *Mahā-bhāshya* of Patañjali; 'slaves and workers' in the Jātakas; and 'slaves and servants [*bhataka*]' in the inscriptions of Aśoka (ibid.: 92 and n10, 166, 197). We need also to bear in mind that *Manu-smṛiti*, 8.70 refers to *dāsas* as well as *bhṛitakas*.

It is therefore rather puzzling to find Sharma moving from this crystal-clear understanding of the three terms (śūdra, *karma-kara* and *bhṛitaka*), as well as of the concept of serfdom, to a bewildering confusion next year in *Aspects*. There *dāsas* and *karma-karas* in Patañjali are taken to be 'slaves and serfs', and it is further asserted that these 'slaves and serfs ... corresponded to the vaiśyas and śūdras [sic! *actually, in reverse order*]'; but in the very next sentence *dāsas* and *kamma-kara* in the Jātakas are taken to be 'slaves and hired agricultural labourers' (Sharma 1959: 81–82)! Further, *dāsas* and *bhṛitakas* in the *Manu-smṛiti* are explained as 'slaves' and 'servants' respectively (ibid.: 194), but a couple of pages later as 'serfs and slaves [*actually, in reverse order, for there is no confusion about the meaning of 'dāsa' as slave*]' in Aśokan edicts in their Prakrit variants (ibid.: 196).

The puzzle is solved by the fact that the bewildering usage pre-dates the 1958 book, pertaining as it does to the chapters in the 1959 book which were originally published much earlier as independent articles. It therefore represents an earlier stage of his intellectual evolution, which he failed to correct in his later work. The chapter on the origin of feudalism in the same book which was written later (Sharma 1958a), is quite consistent with the critical usage of the śūdras: 'So these cultivators [mentioned in the law-

books) were in the nature of temporary peasants and not serfs' (Sharma 1959: 223).

There is therefore inconsistency but not contradiction. Initially, Sharma depended on translations, and was not much alive to the precise connotation of serfdom (despite the extensive allusions to serfs in his 1951 book on world history). However, long after he had surpassed these limitations, a number of these elements in his early writings could not suitably be revised, and are continued through all the subsequent editions of the *Aspects* that I have been able to consult. These are therefore best seen as fossils of a kind, in the works of a person who defied fossilisation till the end.

This does not of course rule out the presence of contradictions proper. E.g., the two dates of the Jātakas that he maintained *simultaneously* in his different writings: 'between the fifth and second century BC' in some works (e.g., Sharma 2005: 22; Sharma 1958: 85); 'not older than the second century B.C.' in the rest (e.g., Sharma 1968: 23, 281; Sharma 1983: 90).

Perspectives on World and Ancient Indian History

Sharma's first major work was his two-volume textbook on world history in Hindi, entitled *Viśva Itihās ki Bhūmikā (An Introduction to World History)* and published in 1951. Its second edition came out in 1953, with additions of a chapter on ancient Egypt, illustrations, maps, and a bibliography, along with 'several' corrections (Sharma 1953: 1). Considering that his research articles do not date from before 1950, it is evident that his labours leading up to the book in 1951 antedate his specialist research interest, and may have begun right after his getting a job following the Master's degree (1943). The significant precedence of his studies in world history over those in ancient India will presently be seen in the book itself.

Despite my very best efforts continuing till date, I have been able to access a photocopy of only the first volume (second edition), minus the bibliography pages. The latter is a particularly unfortunate handicap for our purposes, for the book-list would have been an invaluable guide to the intellectual resources available to and selected by the author. I make do here with the next best thing, i.e. references in the footnotes.

As the first comprehensive document of Sharma's historical thought, *World History* shows considerable promise. It contains germs or leading ideas of his later researches, and outlines his initial interests and understanding, some of which were retained, others abandoned or modified. A couple of examples will help to underline how germane this book is to understanding Sharma's intellectual development. A book composed more than fifty years later is seen to contain almost verbatim reproductions in English of what Sharma wrote in Hindi in the 1950s (e.g., Sharma 1953: 75-76 corresponding to Sharma 2005: 137). Second, in a very brief survey of ancient Indian political history in his *World History*, Sharma, drawing unreservedly on the ideas of Harprasad Sastri and of K.P. Jayaswal, finds

sufficient space for what he calls the 'counter-revolution' of the brāhmaṇas unleashed by the Buddhism-inspired policies of Aśoka, which destroyed the Mauryan Empire and along with it prospects of political unity. In the process, it successfully inaugurated a movement for establishing the supremacy of 'indigenous' (स्वदेशी) rule against 'foreign domination and Buddhism' under the leadership of the Bhāraśiva-Nāgas and the Vākāṭakas (Sharma 1953: 192–93). Sharma quickly grew out of the Bhāraśiva-Nāga postulates of Jayaswal, but, for all the criticisms of the theory of the Brahminical reaction by Raychaudhuri and Thapar, continued to adhere to it *mutatis mutandis* till the end (Sharma 2005: 186–87).

Sharma's perspectives in this book come out as a surprisingly unique mix of what may analytically be described as orientalist, nationalist, and Marxist historiographies. Providing for elaborate irrigation arrangements is stated to be the sole rationale and justification for the emergence of empires in the East (Sharma 1953: 14). The key to understanding Indian civilisation is its ultra-religious otherworldly character: just as knowledge and science are the hallmark of ancient Greece and law that of ancient Rome, ancient India is distinguished by her religion and philosophy (ibid.: 191). She is indeed *defined* by it, with 'the deep impact' of religion on 'every limb of her life', even after making due allowances for the universal importance of religion for the world's other regions, with secular organisation dating from no earlier than 200 years ago (ibid.). In philosophy, no other country ignored the physical world and preoccupied itself with metaphysics as India did (ibid.). This otherworldly outlook is best understood as a product of India's geography: natural conditions here are so extreme and unpredictable that people felt completely helpless doing anything about the world they lived in, and hence turned to the world beyond (ibid.; cf. Majumdar 1927: 9). 'Pure, natural sculpture' failed to develop in India because of 'the preponderance of the religious sentiment' (ibid.: 219).

Indian Civilisation was, however, not to be disparaged for these features. The book has a fair share of nationalist sentiments. The chapter on ancient Indian civilisation begins with celebration of its antiquity, greater than that of the Western civilisation. 'The foundations of Indian legal and social systems had been laid much before the foundation of the city of Rome' (ibid.: 191). Sharma also states that Indian Civilisation boasted of a number of philosophers 'when Socrates was not even born in Greece' (ibid.), without realising that the implied claim to the greater antiquity of India's philosophical tradition is contradicted by his own description of the pre-Socratic philosophers in Greece (ibid.: 120–22). The Mauryas ruled over regions that even the British could not conquer (ibid.: 92). It is due to the all-round progress of Indian civilisation during the Gupta period that is known as 'the Golden Age of Indian History' (ibid.: 194). It is argued in detail how kingship in ancient India was not autocratic (ibid.: 200). Sanskrit is related to ancient Greek, Latin and Russian languages, but it is

asserted to be 'more powerful and richer than these languages' (ibid.: 204), with obvious reference to William Jones' judgment on the superiority of Sanskrit to Greek and Latin. Even the famed painters of the European Renaissance failed to excel the Ajanta paintings (ibid.: 219.) At the end of the chapter, in truly nationalistic vein Sharma returns to emphasising the importance of religion and otherworldly philosophy of Indian culture, but also calls attention to her glorious achievements in material and political fields, and concludes with a reformist critique of her religion and caste system (ibid.: 224-26). This last point that nationalist historians did not just glorify but could also fault Ancient India for her failings, is generally missed in current discussions, and, hence needs to be underlined as a significant, if less conspicuous, aspect of nationalist historiography (for a good example, see Majumdar 1927, last chapter on 'Hindu Society').

Sharma was to discard much, but not all, of this baggage, as some of it continued in its original nationalist form and some other was redeployed as a powerful tool of critique and analysis. While he could later be very blunt in repudiating what he regarded as an exaggerated nationalist historical claim (e.g., the respective roles of William Bentinck and Rammohun Roy in the abolition of Sati, in Sharma 1968a: 87), Sharma is seen to retain as late as 1974 – and there is no evidence of his abandoning it thereafter – a major element of nationalist ideology, namely, that writing of Indian history ought to be a task chiefly of Indian historians alone, excluding foreigners:

[R.G.] Bhandarkar was one of the earliest Indian scholars who tried to construct ancient Indian history on sound lines, and his example was followed by a host of other scholars. But the discovery of new sources and the appearance of new historical ideas and methods make it imperative that we have a fresh look at our past. The work done in this direction by foreign scholars has not been always satisfactory; the primary responsibility of reconstructing Indian history is that of Indian historians. (Sharma 1974: 1).

This passage brings home the continuity of a sentiment that dates, in print, at least to the joint venture of Dr Rajendra Prasad and Sir Jadunath Sarkar in 1937 – *New History of Indian People* – that was to be written exclusively by Indians alone, as 'national' historians. As Sarkar wrote in his Foreword to volume VI of the series, the first to come out, reproducing his 1937 correspondence with Prasad:

This History is being written entirely by Indians. ...

The first duty of our national historian will be to depict all the aspects of our nation's life in the past usually ignored by foreign writers, who merely give us an unrelieved picture of bloodshed and dynastic change. ... In addition, we shall try to explain, *with that sympathetic insight which only a native can possess* – or a rare foreigner like the gifted Sister Nivedita – why things happened with our ancestors as they did actually happen. (Sarkar 1946: vi; emphasis added).

This is the furthest that Sharma could move away, not just from Marxist internationalism, but also from the truly *vasudhaiva-kuṭumbakam* spirit of scientific enquiry, in denying Indian history-writing all the advantages of non-participant observation.

Some key ingredients of Sharma's distinctive approach are already in place. First, there is the perspective of comparative history, which hardly ever leaves its pages, being there in some way, if only subliminally. Historical comparisons may take the form of simple parallels, as when the Sphinx is likened to Nṛi-siṃha, Amenhotep III to Shāhjahān, and papyrus to birch leaf (Sharma 1953: 16, 22, 34). Or they could be exercises in comparison and contrast, wherein we see, for example, extended discussions of the varying importance of slavery in different social formations, in ancient Egypt and Babylon and in India, Greece, and Rome (ibid.: 30–31, 198), or the similarity of the state control of economy in Egypt to that in Mauryan India (ibid.: 199). Also noteworthy is the attention to feudalism *as a theme in comparative history*. Sharma refers to all kinds of 'feudalism', including one in India – as and when he found them in his readings – from early on (ibid.: 32, 33, 47, 174). However, the running methodological undercurrent surfaces only when he comes to treat 'The Feudal System and Medieval Europe'. The big Chapter Ten opens by first noting the wide prevalence 'before the advent of the Modern Industrial Age of the feudal system in various forms in China, Japan, India, West Asia, Egypt, and Europe'; and then sets itself the task of 'considering what its form was in Medieval Europe' (ibid.: 268, see also 276), having already noted in passing an important difference between European and Caliphal feudalism (ibid.: 250). One of its specific features, treated in some detail and presaging a major strand of Sharma's work, is the self-sufficient 'natural economy' of the feudal system (save 'some salt and iron') – hence trade and urbanisation as its solvent, though not neglecting the peasant rebellions and 'their underlying economic logic' (ibid.: 284–85, 298–304).

In the context of Indian historiography, an advantage of the comparative perspective is seen in his discussion of 'the nature of the Islamic Civilisation' (ibid.: 246–49). Sharma prefers the adjective 'Islamic' over 'Arab' and 'Saracen' as more appropriate (and would doubtless have gone in for 'Islamicate' later), but then goes on to detail its composite 'multi-coloured' (बहुसंगी) character as the true 'inheritor of all ancient civilisations' – Greek, Chinese, Persian, Indian, etc. About the Indian impact, he gives the following from E.B. Havell: 'It was India, not Greece, that taught Islam in the impressionable years of its youth, formed its philosophy and esoteric religious ideals, and inspired its most characteristic expression in literature, art, and architecture.' This statement, affirmed by Rushbrook Williams, has been a staple of nationalist-inspired writings. However, as with some other

assertions of Havell, several good historians have remained non-committal if not sceptical about it, e.g. S.R. Sharma who did not wish to be 'so partisan' (Sharma 1948: 264). Nor did R.S. Sharma, surely on account of his comparative-historical sensibility, as he stayed non-committal and drew attention to the differing view of another historian (Edward M. Hulme, *The Middle Ages*) that the greatest was the Persian, not Indian, influence (Sharma 1953: 248).

Religion has a special importance in Sharma's account of world history, for the reason, as he put it in the preface to the first edition (1951), that 'till (the end of) the Middle Ages', religion exerted a deep influence on human society. He saw the all-round hold of religion on all spheres of life in the pre-capitalist world (near overwhelming in India). The importance of religion is seen at every step, the Babylonians for example being said to have strong religious proclivities 'like all ancient peoples' (Sharma 1953: 55). Religion is a salient feature of all the chapters, the pivotal one for a good many of them – from the religious reform movements of the sixth century BC through the rise and expansion of Islam to the European Reformation. It is from this perspective (rather than one of economic 'determinism') that he would develop his analyses of ancient Indian polity, having rid himself of the otherworldly and metaphysical banalities.

The book offers crucial evidence of Sharma's passage to ancient Indian history via his *World History*. Thus, for the opinion of 'some' that there was greater literacy during the Mauryan than the British period, Sharma refers to the world-history book by James E. Swain (Sharma 1953: 203) rather than to the 'some' themselves (not named by Swain), i.e., A.S. Altekar in *Education in Ancient India* or Vincent Smith in *Oxford History of India* (Altekar 1934: Chapter VI, 352; Smith 1919: 114). Second, Sharma here subscribes to the religious otherworldliness of ancient Indian people, whereas Indian historians had for quite some time been effectively questioning it in acclaimed widely-read works (Majumdar 1918: i; idem 1927: 284). Likewise, from Ralph Turner's world history Sharma gained the insight that it is their religion that prevents Jains from pursuing agriculture and confines them to urban trades (Sharma 1953: 74). Next, the 'modern author' who is said to have ascribed the enhanced concern with banning beef-eating in the Gupta period to the Buddhist propagation of *ahimsā* (ibid.: 79) is B.R. Ambedkar, the author of *The Untouchables* (Ambedkar 1948: 119–21). It was via Ambedkar again that Sharma was first introduced to the views of P.V. Kane on beef-eating in ancient India (Sharma 1953: 79–80). So when Sharma underlines the economic value of the doctrine of *ahimsā* in checking the destruction of animal wealth in sacrifices (ibid.: 79, also 71), it is evident that the root idea, which would culminate in his essay on the material milieu of Buddhism, was Ambedkar's explanation of Buddhism's popularity in terms of the economic appeal of *ahimsā* (Ambedkar 1948: 117).

In 1956, in the preface to his doctoral thesis on *Śūdras in Ancient India*, Sharma wrote that he 'took up the study of this subject about ten years ago' (Sharma 1956), that is about 1946 – the same year that Ambedkar published his book on the śūdras. In fact, going by the available list of his publications (K.M. Shrimali in Jha, ed. 2014: 31), in 1950 Sharma published no less than six articles on śūdras in ancient India. That is, the only thing he could not help diverting to in the thick of finishing his two-volume world history, the one *major* distraction he permitted himself, was the ancient history of śūdras. This was followed by a phase of some four years when he was led by his teaching assignment to concentrate on ancient Indian polity, in tandem with the caste system (Sharma 1959: ix), before he left for London to return to and complete his śūdra studies.

The impact of Ambedkar on Sharma was both immediate and far-reaching in all these, but hardly in other, respects. He, for instance, had little use for Ambedkar's passionate plea that the śūdras were not slaves but originally kshatriyas. Also, in contrast to Sharma's zealous interest in gender history, Ambedkar was little concerned with women in these two books, except to use the common exclusion of women and śūdras from the right to initiation (*upanayana*) to argue that initially śūdras, like women, had that right and thus a higher status.

However, it was the other, *minor* distraction of Dange's book that Sharma drew closer to – naturally enough, given his developing Marxism (to be discussed presently). He was completely persuaded by its combined attention to both women and śūdras, and its radical stand that both had been reduced to slavery – women from the once high position of matriarchs, śūdras from their position as Dāsas and the Daityas, the arch opponents of the Aryans.

One of the six 1950 pieces was the already discussed one of the combined references to śūdras and women in ancient India; it established once and for all which side of the Marxist fence Sharma was to going to be on. Further to our previous discussion of it, its novelty lay not in the choice but in the treatment of the topic. Women-śūdra juxtaposition was fairly common knowledge; Kane had already provided a fair number of references (Kane 1941: 594–95). Sharma did not just add some more, but insisted that the combined references be understood as a part of a 'patriarchal class-divided society' (पितृसत्तात्मक वर्गविभाजित समाज), and a product of 'patriarchal class-dominance' (पितृसत्तात्मक वर्गप्रभुत्व) (Sharma 1950: 189, 190). Class and patriarchy – the guiding ideas of Dange's book – were the central concerns of Sharma too in this early phase.

Towards Marxism

Sharma recurrently deployed the Marxian category of class in his account of world history. The *varṇa* system of ancient India is asserted to be but one type of 'class-division', though 'uniquely illiberal and harsh' (ibid.: 198),

and the autonomy of her local administration is not detailed without noting the domination of the village panchayat by 'upper classes' (ibid.: 200-01). The Magna Carta was meant to protect the 'class interests' of the feudal lords (ibid.: 286-87). Class formation resulting from division of labour is conceived as historically a necessary step for 'increase in production and social progress' (ibid.: 226). Equally pertinent is the concern with exploitation and rebellion: see especially, besides the details of 'anarchy' in ancient Egypt on pp. 17-18, and the section on Judaism centred on 'class differentiation' and 'class struggle', p. 92 ff., the moving statement on p. 291 of Pope Innocent III on the plight of serfs in feudal Europe, as quoted in the celebrated English Marxist A.L. Morton's *A People's History of England*. 'Superficially religion and economy appear to be unconnected, but contemporary economic conditions left a deep impact on the Reformation' (ibid.: 350). Ever on the lookout for radical matter, Sharma would extract it out of volumes of all kinds of information; for one such statement from a routine general survey, vide the statement on Prophet Amos on p. 95, citing from *World History* edited by M.N. Weech (the article is by E.H. Weech). All of this sets apart Sharma's world history from other world histories penned by his contemporaries in India, e.g. one by the distinguished medievalist S.R. Sharma (1948), besides putting him in the league of fellow workers like Mohammad Habib, who, with an equally original understanding of the Marxist theory of history, was laying down about the same time his own radical version of world history in his Introduction to a new edition of the second volume of Elliot and Dowson's *History of India as Told by its Own Historians*.

Alongside class, gender figures as the other key concern. World history itself is conceived as the story of the 'patriarchal class-divided society we live in' (Sharma 1953: 4). The dominance of the patriarchal set-up is mentioned together with deepening of class divisions (Sharma 1953: 53). Matriarchy is said to have characterised hunting-gathering societies, out of which patriarchy arose (ibid.: 9). Sharma is acutely alive to the historically different forms of patriarchy, observing significant similarities, variations, and changes in gender relations across cultures and over time (ibid.: 31, 47, 52, 108, 152, 198-199, 233, 255), including the ambiguous implications of developments such as chivalry in medieval Europe, which served to both elevate and lower the status of women in the knightly class (ibid.: 289).

It is significant that Sharma's readings should include a number of high-profile works of Marxian/leftist scholarship, such as V. Gordon Childe's *What Happened in History* and *Man Makes Himself*, Benjamin Farrington's *Greek Science*, Leo Huberman's *Man's Worldly Goods*, Morton's just-cited work, R.H. Tawney's *Religion and the Rise of Capitalism*, Marion Gibbs' *Feudal Order*, as well as *Men, Machines and History* by the now half-forgotten communist mathematician and historian of science Sam Lilley (whose double disappointment at job interviews in

the University of Cambridge had made Joseph Needham so indignant – ‘seeing the better and deliberately choosing the worse’ (Enebakk 2009: 564, 575 n61, 579).⁴

In the small number of footnotes in the book, Sharma strove to advert to these authors as often as he could. For instance, all but two of the seven footnotes in the first chapter on prehistory to civilisation refer to one Marxian work or the other. This served to *announce* his line of history loud and clear.

All the same, while *benefiting* from them, Sharma’s Marxism and understanding of world history cannot be said to have been *founded* upon any of these Marxian works; on the contrary, it was his developing Marxism that led him to cast about for works such as theirs. Instead of being studied, ^{up} these works were consulted only in pursuit of some already-framed query based upon his prior readings. Apart from the specific matters indicated by the seven footnotes, Sharma’s debt to Lilley and Childe for some additional insights is also evident. For instance, for the last point in the big paragraph on p. 8 of his world history, Sharma refers to Childe’s *What Happened in History*, but the remainder of it corresponds closely to Childe’s other work as well as Lilley’s (Lilley 1948: 3; Childe 1936: 78. However, Sharma speaks of the spinning wheel (charka) in the Neolithic period, whereas Lilley had referred to the spindle-whorl on the consulted page, and described the revolutionary invention in the late Middle Ages of the spinning wheel on pp. 43–44.

It is on the first volume of *The Story of Civilisation* by Will Durant rather than on these works that the first chapter remains based, primarily and chiefly. For a couple of telling parallels from ethnography and comparative history that illuminate prehistory, Sharma provides two footnotes from Durant (Sharma 1953: 4), but the third undocumented one too, that of the Omaha Indians (ibid.: 9), comes from the same source (Durant 1942: 16). More fundamentally, the chapter adopts a scheme of three stages of social evolution – Palaeolithic, Neolithic, and the Age of Metals – that follows Durant rather than Morgan, Engels or Childe. (Sharma translated Neolithic Age as ‘Late Stone Age’ – उत्तरपाषाण काल, apparently in accordance with his rendering of Palaeolithic Age as not Old but ‘Early Stone Age’ – पूर्वपाषाण काल.) In lumping the Copper-Bronze Age with the Iron Age, Durant clearly overlooked Childe’s clearly demonstrated sequence culminating in the Iron Age, and thus also the ground-breaking significance of iron technology that Morgan as well as Engels had underlined, and Childe had taken further.

In basing himself upon Durant, Sharma remains in his world-history book – and was to remain so till well into the 1960s – almost entirely innocent of, otherwise lukewarm or mistaken about, *the revolutionary consequences* of the advent of the Iron Age. It was not a question of preference of one viewpoint over the other but one of negligence: Sharma had simply missed out on the relevant portions of Morgan, Engels, and

1 up

Childe. One can hardly avoid running into references to iron when tracking world history, and so, various uses of iron are noted – e.g., importance of military weapons in the Assyrian civilisation, impact of iron technology in China, and the advent of iron technology with the Aryans in ancient India, followed by the great prevalence and unparalleled technical mastery of iron-working – as and when Sharma found them in his references (Sharma 1953: 26, 57–58, 82, 194, 195–96). Yet, the closest he gets to the Childean insight in this matter is only through Lilley, who had named Chapter III of his book ‘Iron, the Democratic Metal (1100 B.C.–A.D. 500)’ after Childe, and gone on to provide a brilliant exposition, actually outdoing Childe. Citing p. 20 of Lilley’s book (i.e. the first page of the chapter), Sharma also calls iron ‘the democratic metal’ in his chapter on Hellenic Civilisation (ibid.: 102). Childe and Lilley had explained how the adjective refers to democratising the use of metal by ordinary people, who had so far been making do with artefacts, including weapons, of stone and wood. However, Sharma thought that iron was the ‘democratic’ metal because it brought on democratic government in ancient Greece and ended aristocratic rule, by arming the commonality with metal weapons as bronze was costly and hence weapons of this metal had so far been the preserve of only the rich. The generalisation was of course limited to the specific Greek case; beyond that, it would have led him to call iron ‘the imperialist metal’ in ancient Assyrian context, where the soldiers using iron weapons helped to establish a powerful empire (ibid.: 57–58), and, likewise, ‘the anarchic metal’ in Zhou China where its use brought about ‘disorder and anarchy all around’ (ibid.: 82)!

Even more fundamental was Sharma’s dependence on Durant for the idea and emergence of civilisation. The latter emphasised three criteria heralding the advent of civilisation – ‘metals, writing and the state’ (Durant 1942: 102); the former does the same: ‘किन्तु अभी “सभ्य” होने के लिए कुछ और वस्तुओं की आवश्यकता थी – धातुओं का प्रयोग, लेखन-कला और राज्य की स्थापना’ (Sharma 1953: 10). Having traced the beginnings to the regular production of surplus to the advent of agriculture (ibid.: 8), Sharma concludes that the rise of civilisation was necessitated by such things as class divisions, a complex division of labour, private property, etc. (ibid.: 11, 13). Those who have known Durant for his critique of socialism and the Soviet Union, or even for his *Lessons of History*, will be surprised to read his following summary of the rise of civilisation in the book Sharma was consulting, which is as insightfully Marxist as one could wish for:

Gradually ... the comparative equality of natural society was replaced by inequality and class divisions. ... Slowly the increasing complexity of tools and trades subjected the unskilled or weak to the skilled or strong. ... Inheritance added superior opportunity to superior possessions, and stratified once homogeneous societies into a maze of classes and castes. Rich and poor became disruptively conscious of wealth and poverty; the class war began to

run as a red thread through all history; and the state arose as an indispensable instrument for the regulation of classes, the protection of property, the waging of war, and the organisation of peace. (Durant 1942: 20).

It is only in one revealing respect that Sharma takes a view directly opposite to Durant's – on promiscuity and group marriage in the hoary pre-marriage age of the human past. Durant referred to many cross-cultural instances of them, as well as some more of their supposed survivals in later times, right up to the *jus primae noctis* of medieval Europe (Durant 1942: 37ff.). He also described, in a rich but complex discussion, the greater say of women in hunting-gathering societies by the fact that women do all work except hunting (ibid.: 33–34). None of this was however to be taken as an indication of, or confused with, a putative stage of matriarchy preceding patriarchy; Durant cited a number of authorities to reject the idea of “matriarchate” ... the rule of women over men’ (ibid.: 32 and 957 n34). Sharma for his part (1953: 4–5) brought in the additional testimony of the Mahābhārata and the Purāṇas for promiscuity and group marriage, but, *contra* Durant's firm rejection of the idea of the matriarchal stage, insisted that all this *was* matriarchy, and exactly *because* the women do all work except hunting – Durant is invoked and set aside in the same breath!

Most probably because Dange's advocacy of matriarchy weighed more with Sharma than Durant's dismissal of it. To Dange, the thesis of ‘the slavery of woman’ was incumbent upon ‘the fall of matriarchy’. He therefore resolved – ‘in spite of the male historian and his society’ – to summon every possible resource for establishing matriarchy based on promiscuity and group-marriage in ancient India, through its countless supposed ‘survivals in custom and tradition’ (Dange 1949: 74). Sharma went the whole hog with Dange: he could actively endorse what was probably the weakest, almost fantastic, element of Dange's account of promiscuity in ancient India – namely, seeing promiscuity in the Mahābhārata passage on children being born in Kṛita and Tretā ages just by resolution or touch, before they began to be produced through sexual intercourse (Sharma 1952a: 118–19 and n9).

Marxism and Ancient Indian History

Even as he came under the growing influence of Dange's work, Sharma began to grow out of much of the *empirical part* of it as he struck out on his own, through a burst of restless productivity in the early 1950s. As we have seen, Sharma had taken the plunge into early Indian history sometime before 1950 when he published the six pieces. From now on, he became increasingly absorbed with early Indian history, having less and less time for other histories, still less for theory. He is seen to be reading across a wide swathe of early Indian literature, from the Vedic corpus to the *Pañcha-tantra* and the *Kathā-sarit-sāgara*, through the epics, works of grammar,

Jātakas, Śāstras and Purāṇas. Inscriptions are not neglected either.

Apart from the articles and book reviews that he published just before, along with, and just after the book (up to 1954), the young Sharma wrote a landmark little tract, entitled *Some Economic Aspects of the Caste System in Ancient India*, and published by his wife in 1952. Wearing his Marxist heart on his sleeves as it were in its three-sentence preface, he declares it straightaway as a study in 'the class struggle in ancient India ... within the framework of the caste system.' And he ends with an anonymous quote that turns out to be straight from the horse's mouth as it were.

True to the preface, the essay is all awash with the Marxist category of class. The caste system arose out of the emergence of class divisions through appropriation of economic surplus (Sharma 1952: 1-3), and when 'the conscious producers' did not want to produce for the non-producers, 'there arose the class struggle' (ibid.: 3). The fourfold *varṇa* system is presented as a binary one in which 'the Brāhmaṇas and Kshatriyas were engaged in non-productive activities like praying and conquering' while 'the other two castes were engaged in the primary task of production' (ibid.: 4). From this point on, caste, *varṇa* and class are used interchangeably, where brāhmaṇas and kshatriyas are the two 'upper/higher/dominant classes' and vaiśyas and śūdras are the two 'lower classes'. 'The political history of ancient India is mainly a history of war between the ruling classes of different states' (ibid.: 11). It was an exploitative and hence conflict-ridden system of 'naked class-taxation which taxes the poor and exempts the rich' (ibid.: 17), based on 'the class privileges' of the upper two *varṇas* (ibid.: 19). The fact is, there were essentially only two classes in ancient India:

The four castes of the society could be grouped in two main classes – warriors and priests on the one hand, and the common people on the other. (Ibid.: 24)

The idea of the binary character of the caste system derived from the work of E.W. Hopkins, but that of the exploitative and hence conflict-ridden character of the binary division is directly inspired by Dange's book (e.g., Dange 1949: 105, 130). Sharma avoided historiographical discussions in this tract, but when he returned to the point next year, he was explicit in his acknowledgements (Sharma 1953a: 321 and n93). While the framework was Hopkins-Dange's, the historical reconstruction in this tract (divided into eight sections) was entirely Sharma's, based predominantly on primary sources and bearing some telltale signs of a beginner.

Ancient India is treated as a single chronological unit; references in support of any given point are indiscriminately cited, from the Vedic literature and the ninth-century commentary of Medhātithi alike. The nature of the caste system and of the class struggle undergoes no basic change in character from one end to the other. Accordingly, at the end of the tract, Sharma declares pre-colonial Indian society to have historically been an unchanging one, and argues that the iniquitous caste system explains,

'more than any other factor... the stagnation of socio-economic life in India', i.e., the changelessness of this part of the East (Sharma 1952: 26). An unnamed author is quoted as the last word on the stagnation: 'whatever might be the political aspect of India's history, its social condition has remained unaltered till the beginning of the nineteenth century' (ibid.).

It is the only occasion when Sharma fails to provide the source of a quote. The quote rings a familiar bell, and turns out to be an inexact, but not really incorrect, reproduction from Karl Marx: 'However changing the political aspect of India's past must appear, its social condition has remained unaltered since its remotest antiquity, until the first decennium of the nineteenth century' (Marx, 'The British Rule in India', June 25, 1853, in Burns 1936: 183).

Why did Sharma not name Marx and give the proper citation? Very probably because he read it in some work that was a popular piece rather than a scholarly publication, and which gave this quote without further reference. Sharma probably knew it was from Marx, but not from where in Marx. The quote could be cited, but not the source of it. We may also doubt if Sharma was aware of Marx's explanations for the stagnation (ibid.: 182-84; Marx 1867: 337-39), which are so different from Sharma's.

Sharma's closest life-long associates have affirmed on several occasions that he had early come under the 'much deeper' influence than anyone else of Marxist politicians and intellectuals like Karyanand Sharma and Rahul Sankrityayan (e.g., Jha 2014a: 12-13). To be in their circle was to have access to its popular Marxist literature and discourses. It is here that Sharma was most probably schooled in Marxism, and equipped himself with all that he needed to know to start on a course of Marxist historical research. It was this equipment that enabled him both to look around for Marxist authors and ferret out radical matter in non-Marxist ones. He would pick up more of Marxism along the way, learning and unlearning, but does not seem to have been particularly enamoured of theory in general: he would be interested only in that little bit which had a practical value for the research at hand. Dange is known to have made himself generously available to Sankrityayan in the preparation of his world-history book (Sankrityayan 1942: [1]-[2]). Even otherwise, Dange's must have been a major intellectual presence in this circle. [1]-[2]

Sharma worked with the same Marxist ideas, including the assumption of basically unchanging India, in the articles that he wrote in 1953 and 1954, before he left for England for his doctoral degree. No stages are distinguished within the eleven-centuries-long ancient Indian history (c. 600 BC-c. AD 500) in these pieces, which reiterate his engagement with the formation of 'class-divided patriarchal society' with 'the growing class and sex-distinctions', and reaffirm the 'stagnation in the Indian social system till the nineteenth century' (Sharma 1953a; Sharma 1953b: 425-26; Sharma 1954: 43).

The Turning Point: London Sojourn (1954-1956)

In 1956, Sharma submitted his doctoral thesis at the School of Oriental and African Studies (SOAS). Entitled 'Position of the Śūdras in Ancient India to 500 A.D.', it marks the beginning of a new phase, and thus the end of what I call the 'little-known first chapter', in his intellectual journey. The newness consists in: rejection of the idea of an Unchanging East; identification of several stages in the position of the śūdras in ancient India; sharp distinction between the vaiśya and the śūdra, who had hitherto been thought to have done basically the same kind of work; deployment of new categories of social class and lower orders, in preference to the Marxist concept of class; abandoning of the idea of class struggle in ancient India; revealing the marked imprint of Basham and/or Kosambi in all this and more; the consequent distancing from Dange; and, loss of the feminist perspective. We cite from the *Śūdras in Ancient India* (1958) for readers' ease of reference, but there is no difference in the cited text between the thesis and the book.

Sharma also penned a conference paper in London in 1956. It refers to Marxist historians who have no eye for social change in Asia's history 'because of the basic formulations of Karl Marx about the unchanging character of Asian society before the advent of the Industrial Revolution'. No one is named of course! But this is now criticised as flawed: 'social changes may have been very slow, but it would be wrong to proceed on the axiom that they were entirely absent' (Sharma 1961: 110).

Accordingly, several stages in the changing position of the śūdras up to c. AD 500 are identified – where none had been seen before. Further, it is only from the post-Mauryan and Gupta periods – not from the outset – that the śūdras come to be bracketed with the vaiśyas; till then, sharply distinguished from 'the three upper varṇas'.

This reconstruction is done mostly in terms of the neutral category of 'social class' and its standard synonym, 'order' (generally used in the plural) – as distinct from the specific Marxian notion of a class defined in terms of means and relations of production. To speak of 'social class' is indeed to assure that it is not an economic class. By 'social class' (or just 'class') or 'orders' varṇa is meant, as in the following: 'The question is whether the Arya and Śūdra represent here two social classes (varṇas) or two tribal groups' (Sharma 1958: 31). Sharma liked to use 'upper classes/varṇas' side by side with 'lower orders' for the śūdras. E.g.: 'The Arthaśāstra shows a wide gap between the pay of the higher officials, who ... were recruited from the upper classes, and the artisans who belonged to the lower orders' (ibid.: 155).

The usage, nearly foreign to Sharma's prolific pre-1956 output, was basic to his supervisor's just published *Wonder that Was India*, which translates varṇa as 'class' (understood as 'social class'), but has a strong preference for the term 'lower orders' for the śūdras and/or vaiśyas

(Basham 1954: Chapter V, 87, 91, 120, 128, 210, 298, 322, 340, 391, 392). In renaming his thesis for the book, Sharma added 'lower orders' for the śūdras in the subtitle.

Basham was credited by one of his distinguished students with demolishing 'the commonplaces of unpolitical India, spiritual India and unchanging India' (Trautmann 2009: 225). Sharma's unceremonious jettisoning of the concept of stagnation that he had long held dear may also be attributed therefore to Basham's 'friendly guidance' and 'exacting standards of scholarship' (Sharma 1958: vi).

The Marxian idea of class struggle had little room in this framework. All kinds of struggle are documented in scrupulously-researched detail, drawing upon and expanding his previous work based on Marxian class analysis (especially Sharma 1953a: 327–330). But there is no 'class struggle', at the most 'a phase of bitter varṇa struggle' (ibid.: 281). The details are the same, the earlier analysis gone. This was to leave an uneasy tension in Sharma's mind between the facts and the analysis, that would keep erupting in his later writings in one way or the other.

To be sure, Basham was not in principle opposed to the Marxist approach to history and was indeed disposed to allow full intellectual freedom to his students (Sharma 1958: vi), but he would have Sharma develop a more acceptable version of it. Significantly, Basham omitted to include any of the numerous previous contributions of Sharma, his own student, as a 'significant' contribution to the evolving Marxist historiography (Basham 1961: 292 and n43). Sharma went along, omitting to include any of his own previous writings in the discussion of Marxian studies on early India (Sharma 1961: 113–14), and indeed took care that none of these found a place in the detailed bibliography of his thesis. He slipped in just about two to three references to them in the thesis, rather inconspicuously, despite a much larger scope (Sharma 1958: 26 n1, 38 n2, 78 n8). 'The little-known first chapter' was all but buried. Sharma's conference paper seeks to do just that, noting *now* the centrality of the concept of mode of production in this approach, and cautiously making a plea rather than a case for it (Sharma 1961: 114).

There is a significantly curious gap between the last chapter and the rest of the thesis. The assumption that 'the [ancient Indian] social order worked harmoniously' (Sharma 1958: 141) is painstakingly refuted from the outset, right up to the penultimate chapter (ibid.: 108–09, 140–42, 173–74, 212–16, 252–53). In the last chapter, Sharma goes into a denial mode; having spoken of 'the śūdras ... seething with discontent' (ibid.: 214), he now seeks to explain 'the comparative calmness⁵ of the śūdras in ancient Indian society' (ibid.: v, 282–83, 285), claiming that the antagonistic activities of the śūdras in ancient India were 'occasional', 'sporadic', and 'insignificant' (ibid.: 282). He remains painfully aware of the 'violent anti-brahmanical activities [of the śūdras] during the post-

Mauryan period' (ibid) that he had described most vividly, and so would like to make an exception of these five centuries (out of eleven) to the claim about the 'comparative calmness'.⁴ But it does not really hold for the rest too. Sharma next explains at length a thesis that was never really argued in the first place. This is difficult to understand, unless we assume that he was here trying to accommodate Kosambi's pet thesis about caste, religion and superstition precluding the use of violence in ancient India; e.g.: 'The Indian caste system and religion performed the function of naked violence' (Kosambi 1950: 262).

Sharma had earlier been aware of, but did not pay much attention to, the work of Kosambi, being none-too-pleased with his dismissal of Dange's work (Sharma 1954a: 84). Now, he was 'friends' with, and very attentive to the works of, Kosambi (e.g., Sharma 1958: vi), an old friend of Basham.

It was inevitable that Sharma should have fallen in line with Dange's spreading disrepute. In the London Conference, Basham (1961: 292 n43) denounced Dange's book as 'very unscholarly'; Sharma as showing 'more enthusiasm than scholarship' (Sharma 1961: 114 n99), and, even more acerbically, 'more schematicism than scholarship' when his article reappeared in his *Light* (Sharma 1966: 17 n99).

As Sharma parted company with Dange, feminism fell by the wayside. It was now that the disconnect with his abiding interest of yesteryears occurred, for good. There was nothing inevitable about it.

Acknowledgements: This is a revised and much-abridged version of the Ram Sharan Sharma Memorial Lecture prepared for the tenth session of Bihar Itihas Parishad at Bhagalpur (2022), itself part of a larger study. I am grateful to the Executive Committee of the Parishad for the invitation to deliver the lecture, and especially to Professor Daya Nand Roy for his warm hospitality.

I joined the MPhil programme in University of Delhi in 1983 under the supervision of Professor Sharma. On his retirement he chose not to associate himself technically with any supervision work in the University, and went back to his home town Patna. Informally, however, he remained my research guide, with Professor D.N. Jha as the official counterpart. For this reason, I spent a major part of my doctoral study leave in Patna.

I owe my college lectureship to the strong recommendation of Sharmaji in the first place, which facilitated the approbation of many others – discounting of course the merits of such account as I was able to give of myself at the job interviews in 1984 and 1985.

I am grateful to my friends and colleagues, especially Prabhat K. Basant, Mihir K. Jha, Ajitha K. and Ranjan Anand, for helpful discussions on the essay's theme. Thanks are also due to them, and to Professor K.M. Shrimali, for making available some old writings of Professor Sharma. I cannot thank Dr K.K. Mandal enough for getting me a copy of Sharmaji's *Some Economic Aspects of the Caste System in Ancient India* (1952) – just when I had despaired of it and started working with its mangled reproduction (Sharma 2011).

Notes

- 1 'Terms of Entanglement', Editorial, *The Indian Express* (Delhi edition), 6 October 2022.
- 2 For instance, if you are a Marxist, you should normally be a doctrinaire person without much respect for data. The sentiment is truly hegemonic, as may be sampled in the slip in the following remark by I. Habib about Sharma: 'He knew, even as a Marxist historian, that without the availability of necessary data, no worthwhile research could be undertaken' (Habib 2014: 685, emphasis added).
- 3 The enormity of Sharma's output, with all the reproductions and revisions, makes it a tricky business *not* to ascribe any specific thing to him. Habib kept a close tab on Sharma's writings, and could yet remain unaware of his work on Oriental Despotism right up to writing his obituary: 'So far as I know, he (Sharma) has not discussed the possibility of the "Asiatic Mode", spoken of in Marx's writings on India' (Habib 2011: 1414). In fact, Sharma presented a paper on the theme at the 30th International Congress of the Human Sciences in Asia and North Africa, Mexico, 1976. It was subsequently published at least four times under three different titles: 'The Socio-Economic Bases of "Oriental Despotism" in Early India' (Sharma 1981; Sharma 1981a); 'Theory of "Oriental Despotism": A Socio-Economic Critique' (in Sharma 1991: 77-8); and 'Early Story of Oriental Despotism: A Critique' (in Sharma 2009: 75-84).
- 4 Eric Hobsbawm recalls how 'no known communists were appointed to university posts (at Cambridge) for ten years or so from 1948, nor, if already in teaching posts, were they promoted', including his own example as he 'was turned down for several posts in economic history in Cambridge ... and ... did not get promotion to a Readership in London until 1959' (Hobsbawm 2002: 182; see also pp. 186, 230-31). If so, Lilley may well have been the first victim of the decade.
- 5 That is, excluding the early and the later Vedic periods. The error of ascribing four hundred instead of five hundred years to the post-Mauryan period is corrected in the second edition of the *Sūdras*.

References

- Ali, Daud (2012), 'The Historiography of the Medieval in South Asia', *Journal of Royal Asiatic Society*, Series 3, 22, 1, pp. 7-12.
- Altekar, A.S. (1934), *Education in Ancient India*, Benares: The Indian Book Shop.
- Ambedkar, B.R. (1948), *The Untouchables*, New Delhi: Amrit Book Co.
- Basham, A.L. (1954), *The Wonder that Was India*, New York: Grove Press.
- Basham, A.L. (1961), 'Modern Historians of Ancient India', in C.H. Philips, ed., *Historians of India, Pakistan and Ceylon*, London: Oxford University Press, pp. 260-93.
- Burns, Emile, ed. (1936), *A Handbook of Marxism*, London: Victor Gollancz Ltd.
- Chakravarti, Uma (2006), *Everyday Lives, Everyday Histories: Beyond the Kings and Brahmanas of 'Ancient' India*, New Delhi: Tulika Books.
- Chakravarti, Uma and Kumkum Roy (1988), 'In Search of Our Past', *Economic and Political Weekly*, 30 April, pp. WS 2-10.
- Chattopadhyaya, B.D. et al. (1975), *A Sourcebook of Indian Civilisation*, Calcutta: Orient Longman.
- Dange, S.A. (1949), *India from Primitive Communism to Slavery*, Bombay: People's Publishing House.
- Durant, Will (1942), *The Story of Civilisation*, Vol. 1: *Our Oriental Heritage*, New York.

- Enebakk, Vidar (2009), 'Lilley revisited: Or Science and Society in the Twentieth Century', *The British Journal for the History of Science*, 42 (4), pp. 563-93.
- Habib, Irfan (1961), 'Medieval Period', *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, Vol. 24, pp. 350-57.
- Habib, Irfan (2011), 'Professor R.S. Sharma, 1920-2011', *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, Vol. 71, 2010-2011, pp. 1413-15.
- Habib, Irfan (2014), 'Remembering Prof. R.S. Sharma', in D.N. Jha, ed., *The Complex Heritage of Early India: Essays in Memory of R.S. Sharma*, Delhi: Manohar, pp. 683-88.
- Habib, Mohammad (1952), 'Introduction' to Elliot and Dowson, *History of India as Told by its own Historians*, Vol. II, Aligarh: Cosmopolitan Publishers, pp. 1-102.
- Hobsbawm, Eric (2002), *Interesting Times: A Twentieth-Century Life*, London: Penguin Books.
- Jaiswal, Suvira (2014), 'Secular Historian', in D.N. Jha, ed., *The Complex Heritage of Early India: Essays in Memory of R.S. Sharma*, Delhi: Manohar, pp. 699-704.
- Jha, D.N. (1977), *Ancient India: An Introductory Outline*, Delhi: People's Publishing House.
- Jha, D.N. (2011), 'A "Scientific" Historian', *Economic and Political Weekly*, 46 (38), 17 September, pp. 25-27.
- Jha, D.N. ed. (2014), *The Complex Heritage of Early India: Essays in Memory of R.S. Sharma*, Delhi: Manohar.
- Jha, D.N. (2014a), 'Engaging with R.S. Sharma and His Historiography', in *The Complex Heritage of Early India: Essays in Memory of R.S. Sharma*, Delhi: Manohar, pp. 11-37.
- Kane, P.V. (1941), *History of Dharmasāstra*, Vol. II, Part I, Poona: Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute.
- Kosambi, D.D. (1950), 'On a Marxist Approach to Indian Chronology', *Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute (ABORI)*, 31 (1/4), pp. 258-66.
- Lilley, S. (1948), *Men, Machines and History*, London: Cobbett Press.
- Majumdar, R.C. (1918), *Corporate Life in Ancient India*, Calcutta: Surendra Nath Sen.
- Majumdar, R.C. (1927), *Outline of Ancient Indian History and Civilisation*, Calcutta.
- Marx, Karl ([1867] 1954), *Capital*, Vol. I, Moscow: Progress Publishers; reprint 1974.
- Philips, C.H., ed. (1961), *Historians of India, Pakistan and Ceylon*, London: Oxford University Press.
- Sahu, Bhairabi Prasad (2013), *The Changing Gaze: Regions and the Construction of Early India*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Sarkar, Jadunath (1946), 'Foreword' to R.C. Majumdar and A.S. Altekar, eds., *A New History of the Indian People*, Vol. VI: *The Vakataka-Gupta Age*, Lahore: Motilal Banarsidass, pp. iii-vii.
- Sen, Mohit and M.B. Rao, eds (1968), *Das Kapital Centenary Volume*, New Delhi: People's Publishing House.
- Sharma, R.S. (1950), 'Prāchīna Bhāratīya Sāhitya meṃ Strī aur Śūdra ke Sammilita Ullekha', *Journal of Bihar Research Society*, Vol. XXXVI (iii-iv), pp. 183-91.
- Sharma, R.S. (1952), *Some Economic Aspects of the Caste System in Ancient India*, Patna: Malina Sharma: Lalbagh.
- Sharma, R.S. (1952a), 'Role of Property, Family and Caste in the Origin of the State in Ancient India', *Journal of Bihar Research Society*, Vol. 38, pp. 117-33.
- Sharma, R.S. (1953), *Viśva Itihās ki Bhūmikā*, second edition, Patna: Granthamala Karyalaya.
- Sharma, R.S. (1953a), 'Politico-Legal Aspect of the Caste System', *Journal of Bihar Research Society*, 39 (3), pp. 306-30.

- Sharma, R.S. (1953b), 'The Vedic Gaṇa and the Origin of the Post-Vedic Republics', *Journal of Bihar Research Society*, 39 (4), pp. 413-26.
- Sharma, R.S. (1954), 'Caste and Marriage in Ancient India (c. 600 B.C. - c. 500 A.D.)', *Journal of Bihar Research Society*, Vol. XL, Part 1, pp. 39-54.
- Sharma, R.S. (1954a), Review of K.R. Potdar, *Sacrifice in the Rgveda*, *Journal of Bihar Research Society*, 40 (1), pp. 83-85.
- Sharma, R.S. (1956), 'Position of the Śūdras in Ancient India to 500 A.D.', thesis submitted for the Ph.D. Degree to the University of London, SOAS, June.
- Sharma, R.S. (1958), *Śūdras in Ancient India*, Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Sharma, R.S. (1958a), 'The Origins of Feudalism in India (c. A.D. 400-650)', *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient*, 1 (3), pp. 297-328.
- Sharma, R.S. (1959), *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions in Ancient India*, Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Sharma, R.S. (1961), 'Historiography of the Ancient Indian Social Order', in C.H. Philips, *Historians of India, Pakistan and Ceylon*, London: Oxford University Press, pp. 102-114.
- Sharma, R.S. (1966), *Light on Early Indian Society and Economy*, Bombay: Manaktalas.
- Sharma, R.S. (1968), *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions in Ancient India*, second edition, Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Sharma, R.S. (1968a), 'Material Background of the Origin of Buddhism', in Mohit Sen and M.B. Rao, eds, *Das Kapital Centenary Volume*, New Delhi: People's Publishing House, pp. 59-66.
- Sharma, R.S. (1968b), 'Ancient Values and Modern Reforms in the Nineteenth Century Hindu Society', in B. Prasad, ed., *Ideas in History*, Bombay: Asia Publishing House, pp. 86-92.
- Sharma, R.S. (1974) 'Reconstruction of Ancient Indian History', *Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute (ABORI)*, vol. 55, nos. 1-4, pp. 1-8.
- Sharma, R.S. (1975) 'Problems of Social Formation in Early India', Presidential Address, *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, thirty-sixth session, Aligarh, pp. 1-14.
- Sharma, R.S. (1981), 'The Socio-Economic Bases of "Oriental Despotism" in Early India', in A.L. Basham, ed., *Kingship in Asia and Early America*, Mexico City: El Colegio de Mexico, pp. 133-42; also in S.K. Bose, ed., *Essays in Honour of Dr Gyanchand: He that Blazed the Trail*, New Delhi: People's Publishing House, pp. 55-65.
- Sharma, R.S. (1983), *Material Culture and Social Formations in Ancient India*, Delhi: Macmillan India.
- Sharma, R.S. (1983a), *Perspectives in Social and Economic History of Early India*, New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal.
- Sharma, R.S. (1991), *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions in Ancient India*, third edition, Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Sharma, R.S. (2005), *India's Ancient Past*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Sharma, R.S. (2009), *Rethinking India's Past*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Sharma, R.S. (2011), 'Some Economic Aspects of the Caste System', in *Economic History of Early India*, New Delhi: Viva Books, Chapter 5, pp. 52-75.
- Sharma, S.R. (1948), *A Brief Survey of Human History*, revised edition, Bombay: Karnatak Publishing House.
- Shastri, Ajay Mitra (1982-83), Review of R.S. Sharma's *Perspectives in Social and Economic History of Early India*, *Indian Historical Review*, Vol. IX, pp. 233-35.
- Shrimali, K.M. (2011), 'Ram Sharan Sharma: The People's Historian', *The Marxist*, 27 (4), October-December, pp. 37-52.
- Smith, Vincent (1919), *The Oxford History of India*, Oxford: The Clarendon Press.

- Thapar, R. (1966), 'A Dynamic View of Early Indian Society', *Economic and Political Weekly*, 1 (2), pp. 74-75.
- Thompson, E.P. (1977), 'Folklore, Anthropology, and Social History', *Indian Historical Review*, III.2, January, pp. 247-66.
- Trautmann, Thomas R. (2009), *The Clash of Chronologies*, New Delhi: YODA Press.
- Veluthat, Kesavan (2012), 'Obituary: Professor R.S. Sharma (1920-2011)', *Indian Historical Review*, Vol. 39 (2), pp. 129-44.
- Yadava, B.N.S. (2000), 'The Problem of the Emergence of Feudal Relations in Early India', in D.N. Jha, ed., *The Feudal Order: State, Society and Ideology in Early Medieval India*, Delhi: Manohar, pp. 249-301.

Vishwa Mohan Jha teaches at ARSD College, University of Delhi, New Delhi.